

Supplementary Materials for “FastEnsemble: A new scalable ensemble clustering method”

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Contents

S1 Details of Experimental Study	2
S1.1 Simulated datasets for Experiment 1	2
S1.2 Simulated datasets for Experiment 2	2
S1.3 Simulated datasets for Experiment 3	2
S1.4 Simulated datasets for Experiment 4	2
S1.5 Simulated datasets for Experiment 5	3
S1.6 Methods and Software Commands	3
S2 Additional Results	4

List of Figures

S1	Mixing parameters for LFR networks from Park et al. (2024)	4
S2	Results on the original Tandon et al. (2019) networks	5
S3	Experiment on Ring-of-Cliques networks using CPM-optimization	5

List of Tables

S1	Clustering accuracy (ARI/NMI) and runtime of methods on simulated modularity-based LFR networks	4
S2	Runtime of FastEnsemble for all model conditions in Experiment 5.	4

S1 Details of Experimental Study

S1.1 Simulated datasets for Experiment 1

We used the library NetworkX (Hagberg et al., 2008) with the following command for generating the LFR graphs used in Experiment 1:

```
1 graph = nx.generators.community.LFR_benchmark_graph(n=10000, tau1=3, tau2=1.5,  
2 mu=mu, average_degree=10, min_community=10, seed=1932)
```

where μ varies between 0.1 and 0.9

In addition, we attempted to regenerate the LFR datasets used in the Tandon et al. (2019) study from their Fig. 2. We were not able to re-generate these graphs using NetworkX, potentially due to the choice of parameters. Here we note that Lancichinetti et al. (2008) suggest that the normal range for parameter τ_2 is 1 to 2, while Tandon et al. (2019) set this value to 3. It seems possible that this discrepancy may have resulted in problems in generating it using NetworkX.

Since the parameters τ_1 and τ_2 used in our simulations for Figure 1 are in the range suggested by Lancichinetti et al. (2008) while the parameters used in Tandon et al. (2019) are not, we consider the LFR networks we used in Experiment 1 to be preferable.

S1.2 Simulated datasets for Experiment 2

For Experiment 2, we used the datasets from Experiment 1 as well as 34 LFR networks from Park et al. (2024) (omitting those that had highly disconnected ground-truth communities). The datasets from Park et al. (2024) are freely available in the Illinois Data Bank at https://doi.org/10.13012/B2IDB-6271968_V1.

S1.3 Simulated datasets for Experiment 3

The datasets we use in Experiment 3 are either Erdős-Rényi graphs or are composed of a combination of Erdős-Rényi (ER) graphs with an LFR graph.

The Erdős-Rényi graphs have 1000 nodes. We used NetworkX to generate these Erdős-Rényi graphs, with the following command, where p specifies the probability of creating an edge that affects the density of the graph:

```
1 graph = nx.erdos_renyi_graph(n=1000, p=p)
```

To combine these graphs with synthetic graphs with known community structure, we created an LFR graph with 1000 nodes using NetworkX with the following command

```
1 lfr = nx.generators.community.LFR_benchmark_graph(n=1000, tau1=3, tau2=1.5, mu  
=0.1, average_degree=9.198, min_community=45, seed=10)
```

This graph has 14 ground-truth communities with sizes [45, 47, 57, 59, 60, 61, 70, 74, 74, 87, 88, 91, 91, 96].

To attach this graph to the Erdős-Rényi graphs with various densities, we used the following commands:

```
1 graph = nx.erdos_renyi_graph(n=1000, p=p)  
2 graph = nx.disjoint_union_all([graph, lfr])  
3 graph.add_edge(0, graph.number_of_nodes() - 1)
```

that creates an Erdős-Rényi graph using NetworkX with edge probability p and connects it to the LFR graph created before using a single edge.

The ground-truth community structure for the ER-LFR graphs is assumed to be the 14 communities in the LFR graph in addition to 1000 singletons for the ER graph.

S1.4 Simulated datasets for Experiment 4

The datasets used for Experiment 4 are ring-of-cliques that are formed by arranging n cliques in a ring, with each ring of size 10. We used the following command to generate these networks with the software NetworkX, where n and k determine the number of cliques and size of each clique respectively.

```
1 nx.ring_of_cliques(num_cliques=n, clique_size=k)
```

S1.5 Simulated datasets for Experiment 5

The datasets used in Experiment 5 are from a prior publication (Park et al., 2024), and the datasets are available in the Illinois Data Bank (see information on datasets for Experiment 2).

S1.6 Methods and Software Commands

FastConsensus. The FastConsensus (Tandon et al., 2019) code is available at <https://github.com/kaiser-dan/fastconsensus>. We used the following command to run it

```
1 python <git root>/fast_consensus.py -f <Input network> --alg louvain -np 10 -t 0.2 -d 0.02
```

where `-np` specifies the number of partitions, `-t` specifies the threshold for removing weak edges, `-d` is the convergence threshold and `--alg` specifies the clustering algorithm which is by default Louvain.

ECG. The software for ECG (Poulin and Thberge, 2019) is available at <https://github.com/ftheberge/Ensemble-Clustering-for-Graphs/tree/master>. We wrote a custom script to run it, which is available at <https://github.com/ytabatabaee/fast-ensemble/blob/main/scripts/ECG.py>. We used the following command to run ECG using this script:

```
1 python <git root>/ECG.py <Input network> <Output file>
```

Clustering Accuracy Evaluation The script for calculating accuracy metrics (including NMI, AMI, ARI, FNR, FPR, precision, recall, F1-score) is available at https://github.com/ytabatabaee/fast-ensemble/blob/main/scripts/clustering_accuracy.py. We use the scikit-learn library to calculate NMI, AMI and ARI, and used a custom code to calculate the other measures. The script for calculating accuracy can be run with the following command:

```
1 python <git root>/clustering_accuracy.py gt <Ground-truth membership> -p <Estimated partition>
```

Mixing parameter calculation The script for calculating the mixing parameter of a network/clustering pair (defined as the ratio between the degree of a node outside its community and its total degree, averaged over all nodes in the network, which is a value between 0 and 1) is available at https://github.com/ytabatabaee/emulate-real-nets/blob/main/estimate_properties.py

On synthetic LFR networks, the mixing parameter was calculated using the network and the ground-truth clustering. For other networks without known ground truth, an estimated clustering was used.

```
1 graph = nx.read_edgelist(<Input network>, nodetype=int)
2 membership = get_membership_list_from_file(graph, <Input clustering>)
3 mu = compute_mixing_param(graph, membership)
```

FastEnsemble The code for FastEnsemble is available at https://github.com/ytabatabaee/fast-ensemble/blob/main/fast_ensemble.py. We used the following command to run it, where `--thresh` refers to the threshold for removing edges and `--partitions` specifies the number of partitions.

```
1 python <git root>/fast_ensemble.py --edgelist <Input network> --partitions <num partitions> --thresh <threshold>
```

S2 Additional Results

Table S1: Clustering accuracy (ARI/NMI) and runtime of methods on simulated modularity-based LFR networks. “n.d.” stands for no data due to method failing to return a clustering within 48 hours;

		ARI	NMI	runtime
LFR cit_hepph mod	FastEnsemble(default)	0.9992	0.9949	43s
	FastConsensus	0.9812	0.9947	21m 54s
	ECG	1.0000	1.0000	15s
	Leiden-mod	0.9991	0.9947	3s
LFR wiki_topcats mod	FastEnsemble(default)	0.8486	0.9923	7h 36m 24s
	FastConsensus	0.9540	0.9997	14h 34m 39s
	ECG	0.0000	0.5767	6h 20m 36s
	Leiden-mod	0.0990	0.8252	1m 38s
LFR cit_patents mod	FastEnsemble(default)	0.8511	0.9916	23h 1m 35s
	FastConsensus	n.d.	n.d.	>2d
	ECG	0.0000	0.4673	1d 12h 8m
	Leiden-mod	0.1374	0.7749	2m 48s
LFR cen mod	FastEnsemble(default)	0.8820	0.9882	12h 8m 47s
	FastConsensus	n.d.	n.d.	>2d
	ECG	0.9463	0.9803	21h 59m
	Leiden-mod	0.4141	0.8973	2m 31s
LFR oc mod	FastEnsemble(default)	0.8145	0.9889	1d 3h 52m 6s
	FastConsensus	n.d.	n.d.	>2d
	ECG	0.0000	0.5013	21h 59m
	Leiden-mod	0.1502	0.8378	3m 37s

Table S2: Runtime of FastEnsemble for all model conditions in Experiment 5. “n.a.” refers to conditions where results are not reported, either due to the LFR graph not being available or due to a high proportion of the ground-truth communities being disconnected.

	mod	0.0001	0.001	0.01	0.1	0.5
cit_patents	23h 1m 35s	39m 51s	34m 53s	38m 46s	45m 11s	45m 35s
oc	1d 3h 52m 6s	2h 34m 58s	1h 43m 24s	1h 43m 51s	2h 39m 5s	2h 10m 57s
cen	12h 8m 47s	1h 12m 48s	1h 7m 19s	1h 6m 7s	n.a.	n.a.
wiki_topcats	7h 36m 24s	57m 2s	45m 21s	51m 54s	51m 19s	n.a.
cit_hepph	43s	22s	26s	30s	39s	56s

Figure S1: **Mixing parameters for LFR networks from Park et al. (2024)**. Each condition on the x-axis corresponds to a *different* LFR network, generated based on Leiden-modularity or Leiden-CPM with that specific resolution parameter. No results are shown for wiki_topcats network with resolution value $r = 0.5$ due to LFR failing to generate networks for that setting. This figure is taken from Tabatabaee (2023).

Figure S2: **Results on Tandon et al. (2019) dataset.** The dataset is created based on the model conditions of Fig. 2 in Tandon et al. (2019) with parameters $n = 10,000$, degree exponents $\tau_1 = 2$, $\tau_2 = 3$, and $k_{avg} = 20$, $k_{max} = 50$, $c_{min} = 10$ and $c_{max} = 100$ with mixing parameter μ that varies between 0.1 to 0.9.

Figure S3: **Results on Ring-of-Cliques networks for clustering using CPM-optimization.** We show results for Leiden-CPM, FastEnsemble with Leiden-CPM (in default mode), and the Strict Consensus (SC) with Leiden-CPM with 10 or 50 partitions. Top: impact of the resolution parameter value on clustering accuracy for Ring-of-Cliques networks with 10,000 nodes. Bottom: impact of number of cliques on clustering accuracy for CPM-optimization, using $r = 0.001$ for ring of cliques with varying sizes. “np” specifies the number of partitions used in the consensus method. The numbers shown on the boxplots specify the total number of clusters generated by the method.

References

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